

Most effective tools and strategies for large class engagement: first year students experiences and their recommendations

Kenneth McDonagh, Jelena Radaković

School of Law and Government, Dublin City University, Ireland

Abstract

In September 2020, Dublin City University (DCU) Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences (FHSS) and the DCU Business School (BS) launched a project “Promoting Student Engagement in Large Class Environments”, examining relevant tools and strategies used to engage students in large classroom settings. The findings reported in this paper are drawn from focus groups and an online survey designed to elicit student perceptions, experiences and engagement of large class teaching and learning and are predominantly by first year students who participated in this phase of the research. Those first year students represented 76% of all focus group respondents and 72% of those who participated in the online survey and thus represent an important perspective to be considered in our teaching and learning approaches.

Keywords: *Student engagement; large classes; first years; module organization; module support; active learning*

1. Introduction

In September 2020, Dublin City University (DCU) Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences (FHSS) and the DCU Business School (BS) launched a project “Promoting Student Engagement in Large Class Environments”, funded by the National Forum for the Enhancement of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education, examining tools and strategies used to engage students in large classroom settings. The results of the study were predominantly reflected through the perception, experiences and engagement of first year students, either through focus group exercises, where they represented 76% of all respondents or through the online survey, where 72% of participating students were in their first year. Due to the global Covid-19 pandemic, DCU, like most other educational institutions, shifted its teaching and learning from face-to face (F2F) to almost entirely online delivery of its programmes. The limitations of online teaching which those students participating in the project experienced also had their benefits as it showcased the most effective tools used and communities created under the difficult circumstances, providing examples of some of the best practices which could be transferred and implemented in F2F environments. Furthermore, given the nature and scale of the challenge to first year students (Ginty and Boland, 2016), the project’s inadvertent focus on first years provided important considerations for large class environments and the approaches that could be further considered by higher education institutions. The recommendations of the overall project are grouped under Overarching Module Organisation/Co-Ordination, Within-Lecture Engagement and Post-Lecture Support headings, with this paper focusing on specific active learning tools.

2. Description of the Teaching/Learning Context

The project’s results are based on the 2020/2021 academic year and cover six modules from DCU FHSS and eight modules from the DCU BS. The number of students per module ranged from 100 students to 600 students (see Tables 1 and 2).

Table 1. Focus group modules, semester I, 2020/2021

<i>Module code/name</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>Cohort size</i>
Introducing Law (LG142)	1	320
Constitutional Law (LG1180)	1	325
Historical Geography of Ireland (GY309)	3	120
Critical Thinking for Business (SB102)	1	600
The Financial Markets (EF307)	2	290
Practical Market Research (MG338)	3	260

Table 2. Focus group modules, semester II, 2020/2021

<i>Module code/name</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>Cohort size</i>
Introduction to European Integration (LG104)	1	200
Constitutional Law (LG1180)	1	325
Advanced Torts (LG225)	1	225
Advanced Contract Law (LG230)	1	100
Industrial Economics (EF301)	3	350
Introduction to Human Geography (GY109)	1	120
Media, Psychology and Creativity (CM152)	1	125
Critical Thinking for Business (SB102)	1	600

Based on the relevant literature, three core research questions were proposed (Table 3).

Table 3. Project research questions

<i>Research Question 1</i>	<i>Research Question 2</i>	<i>Research Question 3</i>
What practices are currently used to engage large classes?	How can student engagement be achieved and/or improved in large classrooms?	What sort of engagement different teaching approaches might bring about and what type of community might evolve?

In order to address these questions, and in discussion with module coordinators, the relevant literature on student engagement in large classrooms (Kuh 2009, Trowler 2010) was re-assessed, coupled with comparative review of the modules' syllabi and their virtual learning environment platforms ('Loop'). Based on these parameters, a selection of questions was prepared for both the focus groups and the online survey.

The focus group design and questions were formulated in a manner which allowed to firstly engage with more general questions (What do you like/dislike about this module) before moving onto specific questions related to the teaching techniques of specific modules. The open-ended question format for some of the questions then led into more specific inquiries regarding the modules in question. The online survey questions focused on different engagement aspects of the subject matter (attendance, asking questions, class preparation), motivation (attendance, interaction, F2F versus online), institutional interaction and the role of peer engagement, before noting open-ended questions worth exploring (Table 4).

Table 4. Open-ended questions, online survey/focus groups

1. What are the most effective aspects of the large class delivery, and why?
2. What are the least effective aspects?
3. What do your module coordinators do best to engage students in learning?
4. What could your module coordinators do to improve students' engagement in learning?

Both the focus groups and the student survey reflected students' opinions on the course and syllabus set-up, the presentation of the relevant material, engagement by a module coordinator, relationship with their peers and finally how engaged students themselves were within the module (their invested time, effort, motivation).

3. Literature Review

3.1. Student Engagement

The term 'student engagement' is in itself wide-ranging and complex. Most prominently however, and used within the context of, and the application by, the Irish Higher Education Authority (HEA) is George Kuh's (2009) contribution to the scholarship about student engagement. Kuh's methodology encompasses a holistic approach to student engagement noting it is 'the time and effort that students devote to activities that are empirically linked to desired outcomes and what institutions do to induce students to participate in these activities' (Kuh, 2009, p. 683). Reporting in 2016, the Working Group on Student Engagement in Irish Higher Education, established in 2014 to assist Irish higher level institutions to enhance student engagement, has identified seven levels which can encourage student engagement. They range from the student level to the module, department, faculty/college/school, institution, national and international levels. Each level has its role and can affect student engagement, both formally and informally.

The opportunities each level can provide range broadly but the orientation of engagement can be noted across specific dimensions: behavioural (effective teaching practice combined with student behaviour); emotional (interest, enjoyment); cognitive (invested in learning); psychological (internal individual process); socio-cultural; and, holistic (Bowden, Tickle and Naumann 2021; Kahu 2013; Trowler 2010; Fredricks, Blumenfeld and Paris 2004). Taking a holistic approach to student engagement, Trowler (2010, p. 3) associates engagement with additional considerations such as 'student feedback, student representation, student approaches to learning, institutional organisation, learning spaces, architectural design, and learning development'. Furthermore, she notes Coates' understanding of student engagement as 'a broad construct intended to encompass salient academic as well as certain non-academic aspects of the student experience' which includes 'active and collaborative learning; participation in challenging academic activities;

formative communication with academic staff; involvement in enriching educational experiences; and feeling legitimated and supported by university learning communities' (Coates, 2007, p. 122, quoted in Trowler, 2010, p.7).

3.2. Challenges for First-Year Student Engagement in Large Classrooms

Several scholars observe that, amongst other challenges, transition from secondary to third level education is the most notable problem for student engagement, in particular in their first year (Ginty and Boland 2016; Pike and Kuh 2005; Cook and Leckey 1999; Tinto 1998). The experience of first year undergraduate students is certainly different than that of the second years, or some older students (Braun and Sellers, 2012). Apart from financial pressures, considerations of a suitable programme, new social interactions and missing of the old ones, the most important factor affecting first years' adjustment to university life is 'the lack of preparation for and an understanding of the type of learning that is required at third level' (Ginty and Boland, 2016, p. 7).

Therefore, particular considerations have to be made for first years compared to other years when reviewing the difficulties students encounter and how these challenges can be addressed by useful techniques for improved and meaningful student engagement in large classrooms. Within our project, it is notable that first year students were those who were more actively involved, by either participating in different focus groups (76% of all participants) or by taking the time to provide their feedback through the student survey conducted in May (72% of all participants).

In order to tackle the issue of engagement, Ginty and Boland propose strengthening several complementary elements, namely assessing and implementing 'a careful review of course design, developing engaging content, active learning teaching techniques, and an assessment strategy. The key is that the student is involved and engaged throughout the process, from design input, knowledge transfer, assessment feedback and course evaluation' (Ginty and Boland 2016, p.10).

By taking first years' views and experiences and accumulating best practices for increased module understanding and engagement highlighted by the students, particularly under the circumstances of Covid-19 restrictions and entirely online interaction, specific considerations based on active learning approach for both face-to-face and hybrid engagement are put forward.

4. Empirical Methodology/Data

4.1. Focus Groups

Two focus groups were conducted in December 2020, covering six modules, with 10 students participating (7 first year and 3 second/third year students), while an additional two focus groups, covering eight modules, were run in March and May 2021, where 7 students took part (6 first year and 1 third year student). Low participation rate at the December focus groups' exercise was noted and attempts were made to increase student participation for March/May exercise.

4.2. Student Survey

In total, 182 students provided their responses to 24 closed and four open-ended questions, with 72% of the student body representing first year students (n = 131), 16% second year (n = 29) and 12% third and fourth year (n = 22). The survey was sent to students from the above-noted modules. As with the focus groups, the results of the survey reflected a great deal more views and experiences of first year students.

This variable should certainly be considered when analysing the data collected. First years' experience can only be reflected through the online teaching practices, which were oftentimes only implemented for the first time during the semesters observed. Moreover, the general Covid-19 related limitations such as solely studying from home, poor internet connection, no social interaction within university's academic or non-academic activities, decreased social and physical interaction overall, etc. directly affected student engagement within the scope of large class environments. Therefore, many opinions were based not only on the purely online experience, but an online experience coupled with the overall engagement limitations.

Within the survey, several positive aspects were noted as those contributing to higher engagement. 37% responded as Extremely or Very motivated, with 38% Moderately motivated to attend large classes, showcasing how important good institutional methods of engagement are for added motivation. A hybrid style of teaching using both online and face-to-face tools was very welcome, where lectures are viewed at home and subsequently discussed in real time (online) with the lecturer. Finally, the survey results showed that 55% of students considered tutorials as either much more or somewhat more important than lectures.

On the other hand, both within the focus group and in the online survey, the most notable issues raised by the students in relation to their engagement, and based on the open-ended question 'What are the least effective aspects of the large class delivery, and why?' were:

- Range of engagement opportunities with lectures conducted F2F compared to Online
- Lack of interaction vis-à-vis pre-recorded lectures
- Inefficient use of lecture hour
- Lack of Q&A opportunities
- Poorly organized tutorials or online ‘breakout’ rooms without clearly defined tasks
- Lack of group work supervision
- Lack of coherence between assignment and module structure

Some of the more specific comments drawn from the online survey from first year students are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Specific comments from first year students, online survey results

‘Long lectures with no pauses for interaction or opportunity to ask questions.’ (Student #32)
‘When the lecturer just talks for the whole lecture.’ (Student #50)
‘Put less of an emphasis on reading out PowerPoints. It is very disengaging and students can read the PowerPoints themselves, its more about the discussion of the content present on the PowerPoint that is important.’(Student #132)

5. Large Class Teaching Methods: Suggested Recommendations

Linking these observations to the holistic approach to student engagement, several conclusions are put forward for consideration. If the initial motivation to learn and engage is generally present, as the project’s results had demonstrated, then the most difficult part of engaging a student is resolved. Subsequently, we need to focus our efforts on other aspects which can be influenced. Furthermore, as not all modules are run with the help of tutorial sessions, the focus must be to increase levels of interaction and involvement within the large class environment itself. The improvement in these areas could be achieved by acknowledging the need to revise our own teaching tools, including new tools tested during the online phase of teaching, engaging the students themselves more in these new approaches and consulting some of the recommended tools below.

The project’s final report included three levels of recommendation, overarching module organisation/co-ordination, within-lecture engagement and post-lecture support. The recommendations presented below (Active learning tools for increased student understanding and engagement) are drawn from specific practices used during Covid-19/online teaching and learning which first year students found useful and effective

Most effective tools and strategies for large class engagement: first year students experiences

as tools increasing their own understanding and engagement with the course, their peers and the institution and which could be considered to F2F/hybrid teaching of all teaching cohorts.

Table 6. Active learning tools for increased student understanding and engagement

Content presentation
<ul style="list-style-type: none">✓ Provide a short re-cap of the previous lecture, noting questions students have raised via email/forum posts/Zoom function✓ Planned and timed lectures leaving sufficient amount of time for questions and interaction✓ Ask questions about the material covered, to ensure students are following✓ Keep text on power points to a minimum, focus on discussion of content of slides✓ Recognise common questions/issues that could arise from the material covered and provide resources to address those concerns✓ Frequently update platform for ongoing Q&A or a FAQ document with all students' questions/answers available online✓ Provide a short (anonymous) feedback survey asking students for their views and suggestions (during/mid and end of module)
Use of interactive tools
<ul style="list-style-type: none">✓ When teaching online, use interactive chat function where students can ask and answer questions anonymously✓ Use voting/poll/survey tool to ensure continuous interaction✓ Provide short, unmarked quizzes to gauge levels of knowledge✓ Set a Yes/No poll to gauge understanding of an issue
Engaging with the 'real world'
<ul style="list-style-type: none">✓ Post complementary short weekly tasks to read/watch along with academic reading material (video/blog/vlog/newspaper/magazine/podcast material relevant to the lecture)✓ Emails/notices about events taking place relevant to the module✓ Show passion for the module, using humour, telling a personal story on occasion✓ Link module material to 'real life', practical and applicable situations

When it came to teaching practices, the move to online teaching inspired lecturers to bring about new and innovative methods which were broadly welcomed by the students. The recommendations this project cites offer a number of useful practices which undoubtedly can be used both face-to-face and online. Not all recommendations can or should be considered for every module, as each module has its own content and administrative specificities. We should however acknowledge that we can learn from our students and other colleagues and that student engagement can always be improved by improving our own engagement.

References

- Bowden, J., Tickle L. and Naumann K. (2021). The four pillars of tertiary student engagement and success: a holistic measurement approach. *Studies in Higher Education*, 46 (6), 1207-1224.
- Braun, K. W. and Sellers, R. D. (2012). Using a 'daily motivational quiz' to increase student preparation, attendance and participation. *Issues in Accounting Education*, 27 (1), 267-279.
- Coates, H. (2005). The value of student engagement for higher education quality assurance. *Quality in Higher Education*, 11 (1), 25-36.
- Cook, A. and Leckey, J. (1999). Do expectations really meet reality? A survey of changes in first year student opinion. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 23 (2), 157-171.
- Fredricks, J.A., Blumenfeld, P.C. and Paris, A.H. (2004). School engagement: Potential of the concept, state of the evidence. *Review of Educational Research*, 74 (1), 59-109.
- Garrison, D.R. (2009). 'Communities of inquiry in online learning' in P.L. Rogers (Ed.) *Encyclopaedia of Distance Learning* (2nd Edition), IGI Global: Hershey, PA.
- Ginty, C. and Boland, J. (2016). Supporting the first year experience in Higher Education in Ireland: Impact on student engagement, teaching practice and institutional policy. *Student Engagement and Experience Journal*, 5 (1).
- Kahu, E. (2013). Framing student engagement in higher education. *Studies in Higher Education*, 38(5), 758-773.
- Kuh, G. (2009). The National Survey of Student Engagement: Conceptual and empirical foundations. *Special Issue: Using NSSE in Institutional Research*, 141, 5-20.
- Pike, G. and Kuh, G. (2005). First and second-generation college students: A comparison of their engagement and intellectual development. *The Journal of Higher Education*, 76 (3), 276- 300.

Most effective tools and strategies for large class engagement: first year students experiences

Tinto, V. (1998). Colleges as communities: Taking research on student persistence seriously. *The Review of Higher Education*, 21, 167-177.

Trowler, V. (2010). *Student engagement literature review*. The Higher Education Academy.

Working Group on Student Engagement in Irish Higher Education. (2014). *Enhancing Student Engagement in Decision Making*. Dublin:Higher Education Authority.